

EVIDENCE-BASED
TOXICOLOGY

Evaluation Report (Acceptance Note) for TEBT-2025-0006

Submission information table

Submission Title	The Food Contact Chemicals Health Impact Matrix (FCChelix): Protocol for a systematic evidence map
Submission Reference	TEBT-2025-0006
Handling Editor	Paul Whaley ORCID 0000-0003-4021-0785
Number of Reviewers	1 editor + 2 peer-reviewers
Submission Type	Method (Protocol for Planned Study) ▾
Preregistration Level	Level 2 (Open Lab Notebook Preregistration) ▾ (explanation)
Preprint DOI	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14943977
Report Number	3 ▾
Evaluation Stage	Acceptance Note ▾
Evaluation Date	25 Aug 2025
Recommendation	Accept ▾

Editor's Summary of Reviewer Comments

Written by the Handling Editor as a summary of the key points from the peer-review process

The authors present the planned methods (protocol) for a systematic evidence map that will summarise the broad characteristics of studies of the health effects of exposure to food contact chemicals in humans. This should be a useful exercise as such a general summary does not yet exist, and the creation of an evidence map will help researchers prioritise specific issues for investigation in a large and complex literature that is challenging to approach.

During the evaluating process, the handling editor and peer-reviewers recommended revisions to improve the clarity of the planned approach and address relatively minor issues around the context, evidence selection, and search strategy parts of the protocol. Some more substantial revisions related to the data abstraction and data storage elements of the planned work were also recommended by the editor. The protocol was well-received by the peer-reviewers, who made only minor suggestions for revision. The editor was satisfied with the authors' responses to all the comments made in the evaluation process and therefore accepted the manuscript for publication.

Acceptance Note

This manuscript has been accepted for publication by the handling editor Paul Whaley after 1 round of revision in response to 1 round of editorial triage and 1 round of peer-review.

In the editor's opinion, this protocol is a [Level 2 preregistration](#), as some of the data being analysed is already available to the authors, but the authors have likely not analysed data in a way that would allow them to predict the findings of the study (which is anyway exploratory rather than hypothesis-testing).

According to our Registered Reports policy, the manuscript following from this protocol will be accepted so long as the researchers reasonably adhere to their planned methods.

A complete record of the evaluation reports for this submission can be found at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245809>